

Micro inertia driven entropy based damage evolution for polycrystalline metals under high strain rate

Noushad Bin Jamal M*, C Lakshmana Rao†

*IIT Madras, Madras, TamilNadu, 600036.

† IIT Madras, Madras, TamilNadu, 600036.

Presenting author's email: noushadbj@gmail.com

Abstract

A general continuum mechanics based framework using the principles of irreversible thermodynamics and statistical mechanics for the quantification of damage in polycrystalline metals, subject to high strain rate deformations has been developed. Nonlinearities associated with micro-structural defects in polycrystalline metals under high strain rate deformations are homogenized by introducing meso-level intrinsic length scale. Micro-structural linear momentum balance is done to incorporate inertial effects of dislocations using meso-scopic length scale so that continuum principles hold true.

Introduction

Current non-local plasticity theories does not explicitly consider inertial effect at microscopic level while micro-structural defects are in motion(Wang et al 2007) especially during high strain rate deformations. Classical metal plasticity consider homogeneous plastic flow since they consider only statistically stored dislocations in to account. Experimental investigations on strength of materials (Ma et al. 1995) reported intrinsic length scale in determining inhomogeneous plastic deformations. In order to account inhomogeneous plastic flow, one has to consider geometrically necessary dislocations to have deformation compatibility in gradient visco-plasticity theories. Kinematics of deformation assumed here are state of small strain deformations, and Irrotational plastic flow of dislocation motion under the assumption of plastic incompressibility.

Balance of Linear momentum at microscopic level

Intrinsic microscopic length scale can be considered as characteristic distances between defects (dislocations) and/or their characteristic sizes (dislocation cells).Inertial effects have been demonstrated by considering the acceleration of dislocations in the equation of motion with a proper definition of dislocation mass and in a phenomenological way, that can be written as follows (Rahaman et al 2017),

$$\frac{d}{dt} \left[\int \rho_m l_m^2 \epsilon_{eq}^b \right] d\Omega = \int \zeta \cdot n d(\partial\Omega) + \int (\Lambda - \Pi) d\Omega \quad (1)$$

Consequently, the meso-level energy balance incorporating kinetic energy contribution of dislocation motion is expressed as,

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left[\rho \left(\frac{1}{2} v^2 + \frac{1}{2} l_m^2 \epsilon_{eq}^b{}^2 + \psi \right) \right] = -\nabla \cdot (\rho e v - \sigma v - \zeta \epsilon_{eq}^b) + \rho \frac{dq}{dt} + \rho r - \frac{\partial \rho h}{\partial t} \quad (2)$$

Combining the above equations (1), (2) upon application of principle of local state ,final form of specific internal energy rate is given by expressing N^p as the plastic strain direction tensor and D as the symmetric part of velocity gradient after imposing balance of angular momentum,

$$\rho \frac{dh}{dt} = \sigma : D + \zeta \cdot \nabla \epsilon_{eq}^b - \sigma : N^p \epsilon_{eq}^b + \Pi \epsilon_{eq}^b + \rho \frac{dq}{dt} + \rho r \quad (3)$$

It is hypothesized that Helmholtz free energy is dependent on elastic strain, gradient of equivalent plastic strain and temperature. To be consistent with irreversible thermodynamics, Clausius-Duhem inequality is imposed to get dissipation function and constitutive expressions,

$$\rho T \frac{ds}{dt} = \left(\sigma - \rho \frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial \epsilon^e} \right) : E^e + \left(\zeta - \rho \frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial \nabla \epsilon_{eq}^b} \right) \cdot \nabla \epsilon_{eq}^b + \Pi \epsilon_{eq}^b + \rho \frac{dq}{dt} + \rho r - \rho \left[\frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial T} + s \right] \dot{T} \quad (4)$$

and decomposing $\zeta = \zeta^e + \zeta^d$, energetic and dissipative components, consequently (4) is modified as follows

$$\rho T \frac{ds}{dt} = \zeta^d \cdot \nabla \epsilon_{eq}^b + \Pi \epsilon_{eq}^b + \rho \frac{dq}{dt} + \rho r \quad (5)$$

The above expression is further modified using the differential form of Fourier's law of thermal conduction to get the entropy evolution equation as

$$\frac{ds_i}{dt} = \frac{1}{\rho T} \zeta^d \cdot \nabla \epsilon_{sq}^b + \frac{1}{\rho T} \Pi \epsilon_{sq}^b + \frac{1}{\rho T^2} k \nabla T \cdot \nabla T + \frac{1}{T} \mathbf{r} \quad (6)$$

Evolution of damage

Damage evolution is defined by a relationship between damage and entropy for solids undergoing plastic deformation (Basaran and Yan, 1998).

$$D_\alpha = D_{cr} \left(1 - e^{-\frac{m_\alpha}{R}(s-s_0)} \right) \quad (7)$$

In time integration scheme, change in entropy $\Delta s = s - s_0$ can be evaluated from the evolution equation (6) and can be used to compute total damage from (7).

Summary

General framework developed for gradient based plasticity in polycrystalline metals, proven to have thermodynamic consistency in the context of unified mechanics which relates entropy with damage. This approach is robust in a way that all kinds of dissipation in any material under external, internal or combined energy transfer can be physically quantified by damage parameter. By incorporating a meso-level length scale, it is made possible to couple nonlinearities associated with dislocations and could incorporate micro-structural inertia effects. This evolution equation may be further investigated in the future to quantify mesoscopic conjugate forces and a workable entropy evolution equation may be developed for high strain rate deformations in polycrystalline metals. In addition to that, a healing configuration can be postulated to map damaged configuration to investigate the effect of crack closure mechanism observed in certain materials.

References

- [1] Wang L., Teng J., Liu P., Hirata A., Ma E., Zhang Z., Chen M & Han X, 2014, Grain rotation mediated by grain boundary dislocations in nano-crystalline Platinum, Nature communications, 5
- [2] Rahaman M., Pranesh R., Roy D., Reddy J.N., 2017, A peridynamic model for plasticity: Micro-inertia based flow rule, entropy equivalence and localization residuals, Computer Methods in Applied Mechanics and Engineering., 327 369–391.
- [3] Basaran C. , Yan C, 1998, A thermodynamic framework for damage mechanics of solder joints, Journal of Electronic Packaging., Trans. ASME, 120 pp. 379-384.
- [4] Ma, Qing, Clarke, David R., 1995. Size dependent hardness of silver single crystals, Journal of Materials Research, Volume 10, Issue 04, 1995, pp 853-863.